

Expansion of the detective genre and its literary features

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Annotatsiya: Detektiv fantastika gullab-yashnashi XIX asrda boshlanganiga qaramay, zamonaviy detektiv romanning kelib chiqishi miloddan avvalgi asrlarga borib taqaladi. Ushbu maqolada detektiv asarlar qanday va qachon paydo bo'lgani haqida so'z yuritiladi. Bu davrda noma'lum jinoyatchilar jinoyatini ochishning birinchi hikoyalari paydo bo'lgan va bu hikoyalar jamiyatning axloqiy qoidalariga zid bo'lgan barcha xatti-harakatlar oxir-oqibat fosh qilingan va jinoyatchilar jazolanadigani birinchi Injil hikoyalaridan beri ko'zga tashlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: detektiv asarlar, jinoyat, guvoh bo'lish, sir

Abstract: Although the heyday of detective fiction began in the 19th century, the origins of the modern detective novel can be traced back to centuries BC. This article talks about how and when detective works appeared. It was during this period that the first stories of the discovery of the crimes of unknown criminals appeared, and in these stories, all actions contrary to the moral rules of society were eventually exposed and the criminals were punished, since the first biblical stories.

Key words: detective fiction, crime, witness, mystery

Detective fiction is a subgenre of crime fiction and mystery fiction in which an investigator or a detective—either professional, amateur, or retired—investigates a crime, often murder. The detective genre began around the same time as speculative fiction and another genre of fiction in the mid-nineteenth century and has remained extremely popular, particularly in novels. Some of the

most famous heroes of detective fiction include C. Auguste Dupin, Sherlock Holmes, and Hercule Poirot. Juvenile stories featuring The Hardy Boys, Nancy Drew, and The Boxcar Children have also remained in print for several decades. Some scholars, such as R. H. Pfeiffer, have suggested that certain ancient and religious texts bear similarities to what would later be called detective fiction. In the Old Testament story of Susanna and the Elders (the Protestant Bible locates this story within the Apocrypha), the account told by two witnesses broke down when Daniel cross-examines them. In response, author Julian Symons has argued that "those who search for fragments of detection in the Bible and Herodotus are looking only for puzzles" and that these puzzles are not detective stories. In the play Oedipus Rex by Ancient Greek playwright Sophocles, Oedipus investigates the unsolved murder of King Laius and discovers the truth after questioning various witnesses that he is the culprit. Although "Oedipus's inquiry is based on supernatural, pre-rational methods that are evident in most narratives of crime until the development of Enlightenment thought in the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries", this narrative has "all of the central characteristics and formal elements of the detective story, including a mystery surrounding a murder, a closed circle of suspects, and the gradual uncovering of a hidden past."

Early Arabic "The One Thousand and One Nights"¹ contains several of the earliest detective stories, anticipating modern detective fiction. The oldest known example of a detective story was "The Three Apples", one of the tales narrated by Scheherazade in the One Thousand and One Nights (Arabian Nights). In this story, a fisherman discovers a heavy, locked chest along the Tigris river, which he then sells to the Abbasid Caliph, Harun al-Rashid. When Harun breaks open the chest, he discovers the body of a young woman who has been cut into pieces. Harun then

¹ Marzolph, Ulrich (2007). "Arabian Nights". In Kate Fleet; Gudrthe work known in Arabic as Alf layla wa-Layla

orders his vizier, Ja'far ibn Yahya, to solve the crime and to find the murderer within three days, or be executed if he fails in his assignment. Suspense is generated through multiple plot twists that occur as the story progressed] With these characteristics this may be considered an archetype for detective fiction. It anticipates the use of reverse chronology in modern detective fiction, where the story begins with a crime before presenting a gradual reconstruction of the past. The main difference between Ja'far ("The Three Apples") and later fictional detectives, such as Sherlock Holmes² and Hercule Poirot, is that Ja'far has no actual desire to solve the case. The whodunit mystery is solved when the murderer himself confessed his crime.[8] This in turn leads to another assignment in which Ja'far has to find the culprit who instigated the murder within three days or else be executed. Ja'far again fails to find the culprit before the deadline, but owing to chance, he discovers a key item. In the end, he manages to solve the case through reasoning to prevent his execution.

On the other hand, two other Arabian Nights stories, "The Merchant and the Thief" and "Ali Khwaja", contain two of the earliest fictional detectives, who uncover clues and present evidence to catch or convict a criminal known to the audience, with the story unfolding in normal chronology and the criminals already known to the audience. The latter involves a climax where the titular detective protagonist Ali Khwaja presents evidence from expert witnesses in a court.

Early Chinese. Gong'an fiction is the earliest known genre of Chinese detective fiction. Some well-known stories include the Yuan Dynasty story Circle of Chalk, the Ming Dynasty story collection Bao Gong An and the 18th century Di Gong An story collection. The latter was translated into English as Celebrated Cases of Judge Dee by Dutch sinologist Robert Van Gulik, who then used the style and characters to write the original Judge Dee series. The hero/detective of these

² Gulik, Van (1976). Celebrated Cases of Judge Dee

novels was typically a traditional judge or similar official based on historical personages such as Judge Bao (Bao Qingtian) or Judge Dee (Di Renjie). Although the historical characters may have lived in an earlier period (such as the Song or Tang dynasty) most stories are written in the later Ming or Qing Dynasty period. These novels differ from the Western-style tradition in several points as described by Van Gulik: The detective is the local magistrate who is usually involved in several unrelated cases simultaneously;² The criminal is introduced at the very beginning of the story and his crime and reasons are carefully explained, thus constituting an inverted detective story rather than a "puzzle"; The stories have a supernatural element with ghosts telling people about their death and even accusing the criminal; The stories are filled with digressions into philosophy, the complete texts of official documents, and much more, resulting in long books; and The novels tend to have a huge cast of characters, typically in the hundreds, all described with their relation to the various main actors in the story. Van Gulik chose Di Gong An to translate because in his view it was closer to the Western literary style and more likely to appeal to non-Chinese readers. Several Gong An's works may have been lost or destroyed during the Literary Inquisitions and the wars in ancient China. In the traditional Chinese culture, this genre was low-prestige and therefore was less worthy of preservation than works such as philosophy or poetry. Only a few or incomplete case volumes can be found; for example, the only copy of Di Gong An was found at a second-hand book store in Tokyo, Japan.³

Early western. One of the earliest examples of detective fiction in Western Literature is Voltaire's *Zadig* (1748), which features a main character who performs feats of analysis. *Things as They Are; or, The Adventures of Caleb Williams* (1794) by William Godwin portrays the law as protecting the murderer

³ Booker, Christopher (2004). *The Seven Basic Plots*

and destroying the innocent. Thomas Skinner Sturr's anonymous *Richmond, or stories in the life of a Bow Street officer* was published in London in 1827; the Danish crime story *The Rector of Veilbye* by Steen Steensen Blicher was written in 1829, and the Norwegian crime novel *Mordet paa Maskinbygger Roolfsen* ("The Murder of Engine Maker Roolfsen") by Maurits Hansen was published in December 1839. "Das Fräulein von Scuderi" is an 1819 short story by E. T. A. Hoffmann, in which Mlle de Scudery establishes the innocence of the police's favorite suspect in the murder of a jeweler. This story is sometimes cited as the first detective story and as a direct influence on Edgar Allan Poe's "The Murders in the Rue Morgue"³(1841). Also suggested as a possible influence on Poe is 'The Secret Cell', a short story published in September 1837 by William Evans Burton. It has been suggested that this story may have been known to Poe, who in 1839 worked for Burton. The story was about a London policeman who solves the mystery of a kidnapped girl. Burton's fictional detective relied on practical methods such as dogged legwork, knowledge of the underworld, and undercover surveillance, rather than the brilliance of imagination or intellect.

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